

GREEN TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP, GREEN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND GREEN INNOVATION: KEY TO ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED PORT MANAGEMENT OFFICES OF PHILIPPINE PORTS AUTHORITY

SUZIE M. HUELGAS

suziehuelgas@yahoo.com

0000-0001-7054-2516

Philippine Ports Authority

Port Access Road, Calicanto, Batangas City

ABSTRACT

Anthropogenic factors are undoubtedly causing damages to the world's natural resources and the disruption of ecosystem services. As an offshoot of government interventions, sustainable development principle was placed at the core of every development undertaking. This heightened environmental awareness created huge impact on government organizations as pro-environmental behaviors become a prevalent norm. Apparently, Government-Owned and Controlled Corporations (GOCC) in the Philippines have been also implementing programs that are inclined towards environmental protection. This study examined pro-environmental behavior in the leadership, human resource management and innovations in selected Port Management Offices (PMOs) of Philippine Ports Authority (PPA), and its effects on the organization's environmental performance. It particularly assessed the observance of Green Transformational Leadership (GTL), Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices, Green Innovation (GI) and its impacts on their Environmental Performance (EP). This study used explanatory sequential mixed method which draws on the strength of both qualitative and quantitative research. It also used weighted mean, Simple Linear Regression and Multiple Regression in the analysis of data. Results of the study showed that GTL, GHRM practices and GI were observed in the PMOs. Likewise, GTL had significant relationship with EP. It was also determined that GTL had direct effect on GHRM practices, GHRM practices had direct effect on GI, and GI had direct effect on EP. Further, the study also proved that GHRM practices had mediating effect between GTL and GI, and between GTL and EP. However, GI had no mediating effect between EP and GHRM practices, and between GTL and EP.

Keywords: Public Administration, Green Transformational Leadership, Explanatory Sequential Mixed Method, Philippines